

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

ACTIVATION OF TRADE RELATIONS AND GEORGIA'S STRATEGIC ROLE IN CARGO TRANSPORTATION THROUGH THE MIDDLE CORRIDOR

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Abstract

The ongoing military operations in Iran and the Middle East have further highlighted Georgia's strategic role. Due to the closure of the Strait of Hormuz, the importance of the Middle Corridor as the safest and most strategic alternative for cargo transportation has come to the forefront of the international agenda. Georgia, in turn, is one of the key countries within the Middle Corridor.

It is in this context that we should consider the fact that, for the first time in the history of independent Georgia, Georgian Railway is launching a large-scale modernization of its rolling stock. As part of the project, the company plans to acquire up to 50 locomotives and 1,500 railcars, and procurement procedures have already begun.

It is evident that for Georgia, as a country with strong transit ambitions, the development of infrastructure — especially port infrastructure — is critically important for utilizing these new opportunities.

Keywords: Middle Corridor; Strait of Hormuz; Cargo Transportation; Cargo Flow; Infrastructure; Export Potential; Trade Relations.

Intraduction: The role of the Middle Corridor is growing. Recently, the closure of the Strait of Hormuz has had a significant impact in this regard, creating yet another opportunity for our country to handle increased cargo flows. A certain portion of cargo has already started moving toward Georgia, which has raised considerable expectations among some experts, while others remain somewhat skeptical, believing that the state lacks both the infrastructure and the human resources necessary to respond effectively to this challenge.

Reserchobjective: The aim of the presented study is to examine the opportunities available to Georgia as a country with transit ambitions, assess the existing challenges, and develop relevant recommendations; to explore alternative routes for cargo transportation in light of the closure of the Strait of Hormuz; and to identify the characteristics of the existing infrastructure as well as the possibilities for its improvement.

Methodology: The theoretical and methodological foundation of the study is based on the research and scientific publications of Georgian and foreign scholars, as well as data from the National Bank of Georgia, the Ministry of Finance of Georgia, the National Statistics Office of Georgia, and social policy documents. An in-depth analysis of the existing data was conducted, and a number of conclusions and recommendations were developed.

Review and discussion: As you know, due to the Russia-Ukraine war and global crises in general, established and traditional routes have been disrupted. Consequently, the countries of Central Asia have faced the challenge of finding alternative transport routes. The main cargo flows from Central Asia to Europe were transported through the Northern Corridor, via Russian territory. Although the route was long, it was one of the most tested and traditional transit corridors. However, as international sanctions were imposed, the Northern

Corridor was effectively closed, creating a serious challenge for all the countries that relied on this route — particularly the countries of Central Asia. In reality, the main alternative route has become Georgia and the Middle Corridor.[1]

The Russian corridor was long, but it operated under a single tariff system. The challenge of the Middle Corridor, however, lies in its multimodal nature, as it passes through several countries. Since February of this year, another issue has been added to these challenges — the problem of the Strait of Hormuz. Both the Northern Corridor and the Strait of Hormuz create supply shocks. This affects not only the region itself, but also the region's trading partner countries. Therefore, when we say that Georgia's role has already increased and will continue to grow, this is exactly what we mean. Its importance will grow precisely because, despite being a multimodal platform, it represents the shortest route available.[2]

This policy is also reflected in the fact that Georgia has launched the accelerated construction of the Anaklia project, as the Anaklia port is, in itself, one of the most important infrastructures of the Middle Corridor. Anaklia Deep Sea Port. [3]

The first phase of the Anaklia project was completed by a Dutch company, and the second phase of deepening is now underway, with the Government of Georgia actively involved. In this case, this includes the improvement of road infrastructure leading to the port. Anaklia Deep Sea Port is a response to increased cargo turnover as one of the key infrastructures of the Middle Corridor. It addresses the global challenges we face today and is not merely a purely economic factor. Rather, it is a geo-economic project for the coming years and possibly decades. One indication and signal of this is also the interest shown by Turkmenistan. [4]

In the future, we will see how the load and the role of the Middle Corridor will further increase. That is

why we say that the Anaklia project represents one of the promising outlooks for the future, which the country indeed has—provided that it maintains stability in the years to come.

Conclusion and Recommendations: Turkmen Railways is an important partner for our country. This year we have achieved quite good results—the cargo turnover dynamics are growing. We believe there is potential to further improve this indicator. We expect that in the current year, the volume of cargo turnover with Turkmenistan will increase significantly.

The Central Asian countries have strong export potential, and their main partners are Russia and China. If they decide to redirect their cargo flows toward the West as well, then, of course, we must be prepared in this regard. When speaking about Central Asian countries, we have long-standing cooperation with Kazakhstan. China is, in itself, one of our key targets, so that Chinese cargo can move through our corridor toward the West.

As for other countries, they should also ensure that cargo is redirected to the Middle Corridor. Everything depends on trade relations and the potential of these countries.

In this regard, the readiness of our transit corridor is crucial, both in rail, road, and maritime directions. Above all, peace in the region is essential, because the reasons for the blocking or restriction of alternative routes are, fundamentally, war and conflict. There is war in Russia–Ukraine as well as in Iran and the Middle East. Therefore, stability in the South Caucasus and across the entire Middle Corridor route is extremely important.

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